

FRENCH ECONOMIC DIPLOMACY: DIRECTIONS AND OPPORTUNITIES TO USE ITS EXPERIENCE FOR MOLDOVA AS AN EU CANDIDATE COUNTRY

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Abstract. *The place and role of France in the modern economic system of the European Union is stated. The specifics of France's foreign policy, its 20 priority areas and the implementation of the components of economic diplomacy are described. Conclusions and recommendations are presented on the use of the experience of France in order to intensify the activities of the Moldovan society in realizing the status of a candidate country for the EU.*

Key words: *economic diplomacy, French foreign policy, European Union, Moldova, national priorities, EU candidate country.*

DIPLOMAȚIA ECONOMICĂ FRANCEZĂ: DIRECȚII ȘI OPORTUNITĂȚI DE A UTILIZA EXPERIENȚA EI PENTRU MOLDOVA CA ȚARĂ CANDIDATĂ LA UE

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Adnotare. *Se precizează locul și rolul Franței în sistemul economic modern al Uniunii Europene. Sunt descrise specificul politicii externe a Franței, cele 20 de domenii prioritare ale acesteia și implementarea componentelor diplomației economice. Sunt prezentate concluzii și recomandări privind utilizarea experienței Franței în vederea intensificării activităților societății moldovenești în realizarea statutului de țară candidată la UE.*

Cuvinte cheie: diplomația economică, politica externă franceză, Uniunea Europeană, Moldova, prioritățile naționale, țară candidată la UE.

In the modern European Union, one of the central places is occupied by France, a country with a long history and a great language, rich experience and culture. The experience of France seems to us very important for Moldova as a candidate country for EU membership.

Examining the state and trends in the implementation of the concept of economic diplomacy in France, one should note the versatility of approaches and the depth of study of individual issues. In particular, as in many countries, economic diplomacy in France is one of the political priorities of the country's foreign policy. At the same time, we note that along with traditional directions specific elements of France's foreign policy stand out. These are sports diplomacy, feminist diplomacy, digital diplomacy, scientific diplomacy, cultural diplomacy, emergency humanitarian action, tourism, Francophony and the French language, external action of local government bodies, civil society. Among the directions of foreign trade activity in the modern economy one of the central places is given to tourism, which in France is recognized as a priority direction of the country's foreign policy and its management is in the competence of the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs.

The website of the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs, as well as information sections on 20 priority areas of French foreign policy are presented in 6 languages, including three languages of the European Union (German, Spanish, French).

As part of the implementation of economic diplomacy as a priority in French foreign policy, the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs focuses not only on promoting the interests of French enterprises in foreign markets and migration aspects of foreign policy for highly qualified as well as young professionals, but also on recovery mechanisms in France in the post-COVID period. Among the activities of the Ministry in the field of economic diplomacy, the management of French foreign trade in all its constituent functions should be noted. For example, the report on international trade of France for 2022, presented on the website of the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs on February 7, 2023, is of particular interest. It was presented on behalf of the Government by Olivier Becht, Minister Delegate for Foreign Trade, Economic Attractiveness and French Nationals Abroad, attached to the Minister for Europe and Foreign Affairs. The report was the result of a joint effort between the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs and the Ministry of Economy, Finance and Industrial and Digital

Sovereignty. At the same time, the report on the export-import operations of France is presented by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, which is the first partner of the co-authors.

It is important that one of the two key co-executors of activities in the field of reporting on export-import operations in France is the Ministry of Economy, Finance and Industrial and Digital Sovereignty, which is responsible for the implementation of state policy in economic, financial, budgetary and fiscal matters. Its tasks cover various areas of activity, such as industry, trade, services, innovation, as well as the management of public accounts and the determination of public finance strategy (monetary issues, taxes, customs, etc.). They are provided by various departments and administrations that are part of the ministry.

Based on the results of the study, conclusions were drawn, such as:

1. In the current conditions of Moldova being a candidate country for membership in the European Union, it is advisable to focus on the advanced European countries experience in the field of state and economic structure in order to further use, adaptation and implementation of their experience in Moldova. One of such countries is France.

2. Attention should be paid to the experience of managing the French economic diplomacy system, which involves collaborative planning, organization, coordination and implementation of a set of measures for economic diplomacy.

3. The experience of the organizational structure of the government of France as one of the largest and most developed countries of the European Union, where the functions of economy, finance, industry and digitalization are concentrated in one organizational structure (ministry) is also valuable.

4. In addition, it should be noted that the experience of France as a global leader in the tourism sector in organizing the management of tourism activities within the framework of the priority of tourism in the national foreign policy, implemented by the Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs of France, is interesting.

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